

Introduction of Embedded System Architecture with its features and application

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This document provides an overview of how to write an application for the STM32 family of microcontrollers. There are a variety of alternative ways to write an application, but the STM32Cube is a simple and intuitive way to get started. The initialization of the microcontroller peripherals is made easier using this utility. It also enhances the code's maintainability, especially when there are hardware changes that necessitate signal remapping to different pins. Another benefit of utilizing the STM32Cube tool is that it creates a report of the microcontroller's user setup. The STM32 series of microcontrollers are among the most widely utilized in a wide range of goods. They also offer a strong support network that includes several microcontroller development forums. This STM Microelectronics microcontroller family is based on the ARM Cortex-M 32-bit CPU core. STM32 microcontrollers come with a plethora of serial and parallel communication peripherals that can be used to connect to a variety of electrical components such as sensors, displays, cameras, motors, and more. Internal Flash memory and RAM are included in all STM32 models. With the STM32, you may get a wide range of performances. The STM32F0 and STM32F1 sub-series, which start with a clock frequency of only 24 MHz and come in packages with as few as 16 pins, are among the most basic variations. At the other performance extreme, the STM32H7 operates at up to 400 MHz and is available in packages with as many as 240 pins. The more advanced models are available with Floating Point Units (FPU) for applications with serious numerical processing requirements. These more advanced models blur the line between a microcontroller and a microprocessor.

1. Introduction

A system is an arrangement in which all its units assemble work according to a set of rules. It can also be defined as a way of working, organizing, or doing one or many tasks according to a fixed plan. For example, a watch is a time displaying system. Its components follow a set of rules to showtime. If one of its parts fails, the watch will stop working. So, we can say, in a system, all its subcomponents depend on each other[1]-[4].

As its name suggests, Embedded means something that is attached to another thing. An embedded system can be thought of as a computer hardware system having software embedded in it. An embedded system can be an independent system or it can be a part of a large system. An embedded system is a microcontroller or microprocessor-based system which is designed to perform a specific task. For example, a fire alarm is an embedded system; it will sense only smoke.

An embedded system has three components

- It has hardware.
- It has application software.
- It has a Real-Time Operating system (RTOS) that supervises the application software and provides a mechanism to let the processor run a process as per schedule by following a plan to control the latencies. RTOS defines the way the

system works. It sets the rules during the execution of the application program. A small-scale embedded system may not have RTOS.

So, we can define an embedded system as a Microcontroller based, software-driven, reliable, real-time control system.

1.1 Characteristics of an Embedded System

- **Single-functioned** – An embedded system usually performs a specialized operation and does the same repeatedly. For example, A pager always functions as a pager.
- **Tightly constrained** – All computing systems have constraints on design metrics, but those on an embedded system can be especially tight. Design metrics are a measure of an implementation's features such as its cost, size, power, and performance. It must be of a size to fit on a single chip, must perform fast enough to process data in real-time, and consume minimum power to extend battery life.
- **Reactive and Real-time** – Many embedded systems must continually react to changes in the system's environment and must compute certain results in real-time without any delay. Consider an example of a car cruise controller; it continually monitors and reacts to speed and brake sensors. It must compute acceleration or de-accelerations repeatedly within a limited time; a delayed computation can fail to control the car.
- **Microprocessors based** – It must be microprocessor or microcontroller-based.
- **Memory** – It must have a memory, as its software usually embeds in ROM. It does not need any secondary memories in the computer.
- **Connected** – It must have connected peripherals to connect input and output devices.
- **HW-SW systems** – Software is used for more features and flexibility. Hardware is used for performance and security.

Advantages

- Easily Customizable
- Low power consumption
- Low cost
- Enhanced performance

Disadvantages

- High development effort
- Larger time to market

1.2 Basic Structure of an Embedded System

The following illustration shows the basic structure of an embedded system –

- **Sensor** – It measures the physical quantity and converts it to an electrical signal which can be read by an observer or by any electronic instrument like an A2D converter. A sensor stores the measured quantity in the memory.
- **A-D Converter** – An analog-to-digital converter converts the analog signal sent by the sensor into a digital signal.
- **Processor & ASICs** – Processors process the data to measure the output and store it in the memory.
- **D-A Converter** – A digital-to-analog converter converts the digital data fed by the processor to analog data
- **Actuator** – An actuator compares the output given by the D-A Converter to the actual (expected) output stored in it and stores the approved output.

2. Embedded System

An embedded system is an applied computer system, as distinguished from other types of computer systems such as personal computers (PCs) or supercomputers. However, you will find that the definition of “embedded system” is fluid and difficult to pin down, as it constantly evolves with advances in technology and dramatic decreases in the cost of implementing various hardware and software components. In recent years, the field has outgrown many of its traditional descriptions. Because the reader will likely encounter some of these descriptions and definitions, it is important to understand the reasoning behind them and why they may or may not be accurate today, and to be able to discuss theirs knowledgeably. Following are a few of the more common descriptions of an embedded system:

- Embedded systems are more limited in hardware and/or software functionality than a personal computer (PC). This holds for a significant subset of the embedded systems family of computer systems. In terms of hardware limitations, this can mean limitations in processing performance, power consumption, memory, hardware functionality, and so forth. In software, this typically means limitations relative to a PC—fewer applications, scaled-down applications, no operating system (OS) or a limited OS, or less abstraction-level code. However, this definition is only partially true today as boards and software typically found in PCs of past and present have been repackaged into more complex embedded system designs.
- An embedded system is designed to perform a dedicated function. Most embedded devices are primarily designed for one specific function. However, we now see devices such as personal data assistant (PDA)/cell phone hybrids, which are embedded systems designed to be able to do a variety of primary functions. Also, the latest digital TVs include interactive applications that perform a wide variety of general functions unrelated to the “TV” function but just as important, such as e-mail, web browsing, and games.

- An embedded system is a computer system with higher quality and reliability requirements than other types of computer systems. Some families of embedded devices have a very high threshold of quality and reliability requirements. For example, if a car's engine controller crashes while driving on a busy freeway or a critical medical device malfunctions during surgery, very serious problems result. However, there are also embedded devices, such as TVs, games, and cell phones, in which a malfunction is an inconvenience but not usually a life-threatening situation.
- Some devices that are called embedded systems, such as PDAs or web pads, are not embedded systems. There is some discussion as to whether or not computer systems that meet some, but not all of the traditional embedded system definitions are embedded systems or something else. Some feel that the designation of these more complex designs, such as PDAs, as embedded systems is driven by nontechnical marketing and sales professionals, rather than engineers. In reality, embedded engineers are divided as to whether these designs are or are not embedded systems, even though currently these systems are often discussed as such among these same designers. Whether or not the traditional embedded definitions should continue to evolve, or a new field of computer systems be designated to include these more complex systems will ultimately be determined by others in the industry. For now, since there is no new industry-supported field of computer systems designated for designs that fall in between the traditional embedded system and the general-purpose PC systems, this book supports the evolutionary view of embedded systems that encompasses these types of computer system designs.

Electronic devices in just about every engineering market segment are classified as embedded systems (see Table 1-1). In short, outside of being “types of computer systems,” the only specific characterization that continues to hold for the wide spectrum of embedded system devices is that there is no single definition reflecting them all. [5]

Table 1: Examples of embedded systems and their markets

Market	Embedded Device
Automotive	Ignition System
	Engine Control
	Brake System (i.e., Antilock Braking System)
Consumer Electronics	Digital and Analog Televisions
	Set-Top Boxes (DVDs, VCRs, Cable Boxes, etc.)
	Personal Data Assistants (PDAs)
	Kitchen Appliances (Refrigerators, Toasters, Microwave Ovens)
	Automobiles
	Toys/Games
	Telephones/Cell Phones/Pagers
Industrial Control	Cameras
	Global Positioning Systems (GPS)
	Robotics and Control Systems (Manufacturing)
Medical	Infusion Pumps
	Dialysis Machines
	Prosthetic Devices
	Cardiac Monitors
Networking	Routers

	Hubs
	Gateways
	<hr/>
	Fax Machine
	Photocopier
Office Automation	Printers
	Monitors
	Scanner
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2.1 Embedded Systems Design

When approaching embedded systems architecture design from a system engineering point of view, several models can be applied to describe the cycle of embedded system design[6]. Most of these models are based upon one or some combination of the following development models:

- The big-bang model, in which there is essentially no planning or processes in place before and during the development of a system.
- The code-and-fix model, in which product requirements are defined but no formal processes are in place before the start of development.
- The waterfall model, in which there is a process for developing a system in steps, where results of one-step flow into the next step.
- The spiral model, in which there is a process for developing a system in steps, and throughout the various steps, feedback is obtained and incorporated back into the process.

This manuscript supports the model shown in Figure 1, which I refer to as the Embedded Systems Design and Development Lifecycle Model. This model is based on a combination of the popular waterfall and spiral industry models. When I investigated and analyzed the many successful embedded projects that I have been a part of or had detailed knowledge about over the years, and analyzed the failed projects or those that ran into many difficulties meeting technical and/or business requirements, I concluded that the successful projects containing at least one common factor that the problem projects lacked. This factor is the process shown in Figure 1, and this is why I introduce this model as an important tool in understanding an embedded system's design process. As shown in Figure 1, the embedded system design and development process is divided into four phases: creating the architecture, implementing the architecture, testing the system, maintaining the system. Most of this book is dedicated to discussing phase 1, and the rest of this section is dedicated to discussing why so much of this book has been devoted to creating an embedded system's architecture. Within this text, phase 1 is defined as being made up of six stages: having a strong technical foundation (stage 1), understanding the Architectural Business Cycle (stage 2), defining the architectural patterns and models (stage 3), defining the architectural structures (stage 4), documenting the architecture (stage 5), and analyzing and reviewing the architecture (stage 6)

the embedded architecture of a device. Table 1-2 summarizes some of the most common structures that can make up embedded architectures, and shows generally what the elements of a particular structure represent and how these elements interrelate. While Table 2 introduces concepts to be defined and discussed later, it also demonstrates the wide variety of architectural structures available to represent an embedded system.

Table 2: Example of architectural structures

Structure Types	Definition
Module	Elements (referred to as modules) are defined as the different functional components (the essential hardware and/or software that the system needs to function correctly) within an embedded device. Marketing and sales architectural diagrams are typically represented as modular structures, since software or hardware is typically packaged for sale as modules (i.e., an operating system, a processor, a JVM, and so on).
Uses (also referred to as subsystem and component)	A type of modular structure representing system at runtime in which modules are inter-related by their usages (what module uses what another module, for example)
Layers	A type of Uses structure in which modules are organized in layers (i.e., hierarchical) in which modules in higher layers use (require) modules of lower layers
Kernel	The structure presents modules that use modules (services) of an operating system kernel or are manipulated by the kernel
Channel Architecture	The structure presents modules sequentially, showing the module transformations through their usages.
Virtual Machine	The structure presents modules that use modules of a virtual machine
Decomposition	A type of modular structure in which some modules are subunits (decomposed units) of other modules and inter-relations are indicated as such. Typically used to determine resource allocation, project management (planning), data management (encapsulation, privatization, etc.).
Class (also referred to as generalization)	This is a type of modular structure representing the software and in which modules are referred to as classes, and inter-relationships are defined according to the object-oriented approach in which classes are inheriting from other classes, or are actual instances of a parent class (for example). Useful in designing systems with similar foundations
Component and Connector	These structures are composed of elements that are either components (main hw/sw processing units, such as processors, a Java Virtual Machine, etc.) or connectors (communication mechanism that interconnects components, such as a hw bus, or sw OS messages, etc.)
Client/Server (also referred to as distribution)	Structure of system at runtime where components are clients or servers (or objects), and connectors are the mechanisms used (protocols, messages, packets, etc.) used to intercommunicate between clients and servers (or objects)
Process (also referred to as communicating processes)	This structure is an SW structure of a system containing an operating system. Components are processes and/or threads and their connectors are the inter-process communication mechanisms (shared data, pipes, etc.) Useful for analyzing scheduling and performance.

	Concurrency and Resource	This structure is a runtime snapshot of a system containing an OS, and in which components are connected via threads running in parallel. Essentially, this structure is used for resource management and to determine if there are any problems with shared resources, as well as to determine what sw can be executed in parallel
	Interrupt	The structure represents the interrupt handling mechanisms in the system
	Scheduling (EDF, priority, round-robin)	The structure represents the task scheduling mechanism of threads demonstrating the fairness of the OS scheduler
	Memory	This runtime representation is of memory and data components with the memory allocation and deallocation (connector) schemes—essentially the memory management scheme of the system.
	Garbage Collection	This structure represents the garbage allocation scheme.
	Allocation	This structure represents the memory allocation scheme of the system (static or dynamic, size, and so on).
	Safety and Reliability	This structure is of the system at runtime in which redundant components (hw and sw elements) and their intercommunication mechanisms demonstrate the reliability and safety of a system in the event of problems (its ability to recover from a variety of problems)
Allocation	A structure representing relationships between sw and/or hw elements, and external elements in various environments	
	Work Assignment	This structure assigns module responsibility to various development and design teams. Typically used in project management.
	Implementation	This is a sw structure indicating where the sw is located on the development system's file system
	Deployment	This structure is of the system at runtime where elements in this structure are hw and sw, and the relationship between elements are where the sw maps to in the hardware (resides, migrates to, etc)

2.3 Important of the Architecture in Embedded System

This book uses an architectural system engineering approach to embedded systems because it is one of the most powerful tools that can be used to understand an embedded systems design or to resolve challenges faced when designing a new system. The most common of these challenges include:

- defining and capturing the design of a system
- cost limitations
- determining a system's integrity, such as reliability and safety
- working within the confines of available elemental functionality (i.e., processing power, memory, battery life, etc.)
- marketability and sellability
- deterministic requirements

In short, an embedded systems architecture can be used to resolve these challenges early in a project. Without defining or knowing any of the internal implementation details, the architecture of an embedded device can be the first tool to be analyzed and used as a high-level blueprint defining the infrastructure of a design, possible design options, and design constraints. What makes the architectural approach so powerful is its ability to informally and quickly communicate a design to a variety of people with or without technical backgrounds,

even acting as a foundation in planning the project or designing a device. Because it clearly outlines the requirements of the system, an architecture can act as a solid basis for analyzing and testing the quality of a device and its performance under various circumstances. Furthermore, if understood, created, and leveraged correctly, an architecture can be used to accurately estimate and reduce costs through its demonstration of the risks involved in implementing the various elements, allowing for the mitigation of these risks. Finally, the various structures of architecture can then be leveraged for designing future products with similar characteristics, thus allowing design knowledge to be reused, and leading to a decrease in future design and development costs.

By using the architectural approach in this book, I hope to relay to the reader that defining and understanding the architecture of an embedded system is an essential component of good system design. This is because, in addition to the benefits listed above:

1. *Every embedded system has an architecture, whether it is or is not documented because every embedded system is composed of interacting elements (whether hardware or software). An architecture by definition is a set of representations of those elements and their relationships. Rather than having a faulty and costly architecture forced on you by not taking the time to define an architecture before starting development, take control of the design by defining the architecture first.*
2. *Because an embedded architecture captures various views, which are representations of the system, it is a useful tool in understanding all of the major elements, why each component is there, and why the elements behave the way they do. Every element within a device interacts with some other element in some fashion. Furthermore, externally visible characteristics of elements may differ given a different set of other elements to work with. Without understanding the “whys” behind an element’s provided functionality, performance, and so on, it would be difficult to determine how the system would behave under a variety of circumstances in the real world.*

Even if the architectural structures are rough and informal, it is still better than nothing. As long as the architecture conveys in some way the critical components of a design and their relationships to each other, it can provide project members with key information about whether the device can meet its requirements, and how such a system can be constructed successfully.

2.4 The Embedded Systems Model

Within the scope of this report, a variety of architectural structures are used to introduce technical concepts and fundamentals of an embedded system. I also introduce emerging architectural tools (i.e., reference models) used as the foundation for these architectural structures[10]. At the highest level, the primary architectural tool used to introduce the major elements located within an embedded system design is what I will refer to as the Embedded Systems Model, shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Embedded Systems Mode

What the Embedded Systems Model indicates is that all embedded systems share one similarity at the highest level; that is, they all have at least one layer (hardware) or all layers (hardware, system software, and application software) into which all components fall. The hardware layer contains all the major physical components located on an embedded board, whereas the system and application software layers contain all of the software located on and being processed by the embedded system.

This reference model is essentially a layered (modular) representation of an embedded systems architecture from which a modular architectural structure can be derived. Regardless of the differences between the devices shown in Table 1-1, it is possible to understand the architecture of all of these systems by visualizing and grouping the components within these devices as layers. While the concept of layering isn't unique to embedded system design (architectures are relevant to all computer systems, and an embedded system is a type A Systems Engineering Approach to Embedded Systems Design 13 of computer system), it is a useful tool in visualizing the possible combinations of hundreds, if not thousands, of hardware and software components that can be used in designing an embedded system. In general, I selected this modular representation of embedded systems architecture as the primary structure for this book for two main reasons:

1. The visual representation of the main elements and their associated functions. The layered approach allows readers to visualize the various components of an embedded system and their interrelationships.
2. Modular architectural representations are typically the structures leveraged to structure the entire embedded project. This is mainly because the various modules (elements) within this type of structure are usually functionally independent. These elements also have a higher degree of interaction, thus separating these types of elements into layers improves the structural organization of the system without the risk of oversimplifying complex interactions or overlooking required functionality.

Sections 2 and 3 of this report define the major modules that fall into the layers of the Embedded Systems Model, essentially outlining the major components that can be found in most embedded systems. Section 4 then puts these layers together from a design and development viewpoint, demonstrating to the reader how to apply the technical concepts covered in previous chapters along with the architectural process introduced in this chapter. Throughout this book, real-world suggestions and examples are provided to present a pragmatic view of the technical theories, and as the key teaching tool of embedded concepts. As you read these various examples, to gain the maximum benefits from this text and to be able to apply the information provided to future embedded projects, I recommend that the reader note:

- the patterns that all these various examples follow, by mapping them not only to the technical concepts introduced in the section but ultimately to the higher-level architectural representations. These patterns are what can be universally applied to understand or design any embedded system, regardless of the embedded system design being analyzed.
- where the information came from. This is because valuable information on embedded systems design can be gathered from a variety of sources, including the internet, articles

from embedded magazines, the Embedded Systems Conference, datasheets, user manuals, programming manuals, and schematics—to name just a few.

3. STM32 series processors with GPIO function

3.1 General Purpose Input / Outputs (GPIO) is an interface for the MCU to connect to external devices which it can use as input to read data or use as output to write data, etc. There are available three GPIOs on this MCU (STM32F103 with 80 Pins). They should configure by software and they are significant to consider during working with the MCU. All peripherals of the MCU can connect to the outside or other external devices by GPIOs.

3.2 GPIO Configuration

The GPIO configuration selects and enables the microcontroller ports or any pins of the microcontroller to apply for the microcontroller during the task. This configuration defines inputs/outputs and the status of each port or each pin. Figure 3 shows the Pins Configuration of the microcontroller STM32F103. This pins configuration is important to configure the microcontroller ports or pins for programming the microcontroller and it should be considered. The number of pins and their specification is mentioned in figure 3 and it is so useful for configuring the microcontroller pins.

13	VDDA	PB0/ADC8/TIM3_CH3	26
12	USSA	PB1/ADC9/TIM3_CH4	27
4	UBAT	PB2/BOOT1	28
32	VDD_1	PB3/JTDD	29
18	VDD_2	PB4/JTRST	30
19	VDD_4	PB5/I2C1_SMBA	31
64	VDD_3	PB6/I2C1_SCL/TIM4_CH1	32
		PB7/I2C1_SDA/TIM4_CH2	33
		PB8/TIM4_CH3	34
		PB9/TIM4_CH4	35
		PB10/I2C2_SCL/USART3_TX	36
		PB11/I2C2_SDA/USART3_RX	37
31	USS_1	PB12/SPI2_NSS/I2C2_SMBAL/USART3_CK/TIM1_BKIN	38
47	USS_2	PB13/SPI2_SCK/USART3_CTS/TIM1_CH1N	39
63	USS_3	PB14/SPI2_MISO/USART3_RTS/TIM1_CH2N	40
18	USS_4	PB15/SPI2_MOSI/TIM1_CH3N	41
7	NRST	PC0/ADC10	8
60	BOOT0	PC1/ADC11	9
		PC2/ADC12	10
		PC3/ADC13	11
14	PA0-IKUP/USART2_CTS/ADC0/TIM2_CH1_ETR	PC4/ADC14	12
15	PA1/USART2_RTS/ADC1/TIM2_CH2	PC5/ADC15	13
16	PA2/USART2_TX/ADC2/TIM2_CH3	PC6	14
17	PA3/USART2_RX/ADC3/TIM2_CH4	PC7	15
20	PA4/SPI1_NSS/USART2_CK/ADC4	PC8	16
21	PA5/SPI1_SCK/ADC5	PC9	17
22	PA6/SPI1_MISO/ADC6/TIM3_CH1	PC10	18
23	PA7/SPI1_MOSI/ADC7/TIM3_CH2	PC11	19
14	PA8/USART1_CK/TIM1_CH1/TCD	PC12	20
42	PA9/USART1_TX/TIM1_CH2	PC13/ANTI_TAMP	21
43	PA10/USART1_RX/TIM1_CH3	PC14/OSC2_IN	22
44	PA11/USART1_CTS/CANRX/USBDM/TIM1_CH4	PC15/OSC32_OUT	23
45	PA12/USART1_RTS/CANTX/USBDM/TIM1_ETR		24
46	PA13/JTMS-SWDAT	PDB/DSC_IN	25
48	PA14/JTCK-SACLK	PDL/DSC_OUT	26
50	PA15/JTDI	PB2/TIM9_ETR	27

Figure 3: Pins Configuration of the STM32F103

The microcontroller peripherals are available from pins of Port A, Port B, and Port C. So, it is necessary to activate these ports by the program according to the work request and they are 18 obtained at GPIO Configuration. In this configuration, a GPIO clock is enabled for all the microcontroller ports to enable its ports. It is also defined as the ADC pin that this pin is used as an input for the ADC and a pin for the USB circuit (the USB hardware is connected to the microcontroller and it is enabled by using this pin). PA1 (Port A, pin 1) is set as an input of the ADC for this work and the mode of this pin should be set as Input, but the ADC has not been enabled yet. It is just considered as an input pin for the ADC peripheral. PB1 is used to enable the USB device and the mode of this pin should be set as an Output. Program set or reset (1 or 0 voltage) PB1 to activate the USB device. PC6 and PC7 are enabled as output and their mode is set as Output. They are used to turn on two LEDs.

3.3 GPIO functional description

STM32 GPIO can be used in a variety of configurations. Each GPIO pin can be individually configured by software in any of the following modes:

- Input floating
- Input pull-up
- Input-pull-down
- Analog
- Output open-drain with pull-up or pull-down capability
- Output push-pull with pull-up or pull-down capability
- Alternate function push-pull with pull-up or pull-down capability
- Alternate function open-drain with pull-up or pull-down capability

3.3.1 Input mode configuration

When an STM32 device I/O pin is configured as input, one of three options must be selected:

- Input with internal pull-up. Pull-up resistors are used in STM32 devices to ensure a well-defined logical level in case of floating input signal. Depending on application requirements, an external pull-up can be used instead.
- Input with internal pull-down. Pull-down resistors are used in STM32 devices to ensure a well-defined logical level in the case of floating input signals. Depending on application requirements, an external pull-down can be used instead.
- Floating input. The signal level follows the external signal. When no external signal is present, the Schmitt trigger randomly toggles between the logical levels induced by the external noise. This increases the overall consumption.

Programmed as input, and I/O port exhibits the following characteristics:

- The output buffer is disabled
- The Schmitt trigger input is activated
- The pull-up or pull-down resistors are activated depending on the value in the GPIOx_PUPDR register
- The data present on the I/O pin is sampled into the input data register at each AHB clock cycle
- The I/O state is obtained by reading the GPIOx_IDR input data register

3.3.2 Output mode configuration

When an STM32 device I/O pin is configured as an output, one of two options must be selected:

- Push-pull output mode:
The push-pull output uses two transistors: one PMOS and one NMOS. Each transistor is ON to drive the output to the appropriate level:
 - ❖ The top transistor (PMOS) is ON when the output has to drive HIGH state
 - ❖ The bottom transistor (NMOS) is ON when the output has to drive a LOW state
 - ❖ The control of the two transistors is done through the GPIO port output type register (GPIOx_OTYPER).
 - ❖ Writing the related bit of the output register (GPIOx_ODR) to 0 activates the NMOS transistor to force the I/O pin to the ground.
 - ❖ Writing the related bit of the output register (GPIOx_ODR) to 1 activates the PMOS transistor to force the I/O pin to VDD.
- Open-drain output mode:
Open-drain output mode does not use the PMOS transistor and a pull-up resistor is required.
When the output has to go high, the NMOS transistor must be turned off, pulling the line high only by the pull-up resistor. This pull-up resistor could be internal with a

typical value of 40 k ohm and activated through GPIO port pull-up / pull-down register (GPIOx_PUPDR).

Note: It is important to note that it is not possible to activate pull-up and pull-down at the same time on the same I/O pin.

It is also possible to use an external pull-up or pull-down resistor instead of the internal resistor. In this case, the value must be adapted to be compliant with the GPIO output voltage and current characteristics.

Programmed as output, and I/O port exhibits the following characteristics:

- The output buffer can be configured in open-drain or push-pull mode
- The Schmitt trigger input is activated
- The internal pull-up and pull-down resistors are activated depending on the value in the GPIOx_PUPDR register.
- The written value into the output data register GPIOx_ODR sets the I/O pin state
- The written data on GPIOx_ODR can be read from the GPIOx_IDR register that is updated every AHB clock cycle

Open-drain output is often used to control devices which operate at a different voltage supply than the STM32. Open-drain mode is also used to drive one or several I²C devices when specific pull-up resistors are required. GPIO functional description AN4899

3.3.3 Alternate functions

On some STM32 GPIO pins, the user can select alternate functions inputs/outputs. Each pin is multiplexed with up to sixteen peripheral functions such as communication interfaces (SPI, UART, I²C, USB, CAN, LCD and others), timers, debug interface, and others.

The alternate function of the selected pin is configured through two registers:

- GPIOx_AFRH (for pin 0 to 7)
- GPIOx_AFRH (for pin 8 to 15)

To know which functions are multiplexed on each GPIO pin, refer to the device datasheet.

When the I/O port is programmed as alternate function mode:

- The output buffer can be configured in open-drain or push-pull mode
- The output buffer is driven by the signals coming from the peripheral (transmitter enable and data)
- The Schmitt trigger input is activated
- The pull-up and pull-down resistors activations depend on the value in the register
- GPIOx_PUPDR

The data present on the I/O pin are sampled into the input data register at each AHB clock cycle. Read access to the input data register provides the I/O state. Alternate functions details are provided in the datasheet and the reference manual of the product.

3.3.4 Analog configuration

Few STM32 GPIO pins can be configured in an analog mode which allows the use of ADC, DAC, OPAMP, and COMP internal peripherals. To use a GPIO pin in analog mode, the following register is considered:

- GPIOx_MODER to select the mode (Input, Output, Alternate, Analog)
- GPIOx_ASCR to select the required function ADC, DAC, OPAMP, or COMP

When the I/O port is programmed in an analog configuration:

- The output buffer is disabled

- The Schmitt trigger input is deactivated, providing zero consumption for every analog value of the I/O pin. The output of the Schmitt trigger is forced to a constant value (0).
- The pull-up and pull-down resistors are disabled by hardware

Read access to the input data register gets the value 0.

For details concerning ADC, DAC, OPAMP, and COMP function and programming, refer to the datasheet and reference manual of the product.

The analog switch itself is not closed. The analog switch is closed only when the analog peripheral is selected (or enabled) on the given pin.

4. STM32 serial communication

4.1 Serial communication

Serial communication refers to a communication mode in which data is transmitted bit by bit between peripherals and computers through data lines, ground wires, and control lines. This communication mode uses fewer data lines, which can save the communication cost in long-distance communication, but its transmission speed is slower than parallel transmission.

4.2 Serial communication protocol

In computer science, most complex problems can be simplified by layering. For example, the chip is divided into core layer and on-chip peripherals. STM32 standard library is the software layer between register and user code. We also understand the communication protocol hierarchically. The most basic thing is to divide it into the physical layer and protocol layer. In short, the physical layer specifies whether we communicate with our mouth or limbs, and the protocol layer specifies whether we communicate in Chinese or English. The physical layer specifies the characteristics of mechanical and electronic functional parts in the communication system to ensure the transmission of original data in physical media, eg: RS232, TTL high and low levels. The protocol layer mainly specifies the communication logic and unifies the data packaging and unpacking standards of both sending and receiving sides. Eg: serial port data packet: a start bit, data bit (8bit), check bit, and stop bit.

4.2.1 Start bit:

It is in the logic "1" state when there is no data transmission on the communication line. When the transmitting device sends a character data, it first sends a logic "0" signal, and this logic low level is the start bit (falling edge). The start bit is transmitted to the receiving device through the communication line. When the receiving device detects this logic low level, it starts to prepare to receive the data signal. Therefore, the function of the start bit is to indicate the beginning of character transmission.

4.2.2 Data bits:

This is a parameter that measures the actual data bits in communication. When the computer sends a packet, the actual data will not be 8 bits, and the standard values are 5, 7, and 8 bits. How you set it depends on the message you want to send. For example, the standard ASCII code is 0 ~ 127 (7 bits). The extended ASCII code is 0 ~ 255 (8 bits). If the data uses simple text (standard ASCII code), each packet uses 7 bits of data. Each packet refers to a byte, including start/stop bits, data bits, and parity

bits. Since the actual data bits depend on the selection of the communication protocol, the term "packet" refers to any communication situation.

4.2.3 Stop bit:

Used to represent the last bit of a single package. Typical values are 1, 1.5, and 2 bits. Because the data is timed on the transmission line and each device has its clock, there may be a small synchronization between the two devices in the communication. Therefore, the stop bit not only indicates the end of transmission but also provides an opportunity for the computer to correct clock synchronization. The more bits applicable to stop bits, the greater the tolerance of different clock synchronization, but the slower the data transmission rate.

4.2.4 Parity bit:

A simple error detection method in serial communication. There are four error detection methods: even, odd, high, and low. Of course, it is OK to have no check bit. For even and odd parity, the serial port will set the parity bit (one bit after the data bit) and use a value to ensure that the transmitted data has even or odd logical high bits. For example, if the data is 011, for even parity, the parity bit is 0 to ensure that the number of digits with high logic is even. If it is an odd check, the check bit is 1, so there are three logical high bits. The high and low bits do not check the data. Simply set the logic high or logic low check. In this way, the receiving device can know the state of one bit and have the opportunity to judge whether there is noise interfering with the communication or whether the transmission and reception data are not synchronized.

4.3 serial communication between STM32 and computer

Universal Asynchronous Receiver/Transmitter (UART) for short represents the hardware circuitry (module) being used for serial communication. UART is sold/shipped as a standalone integrated circuit (IC) or as an internal module within microcontrollers. In this tutorial, we're concerned with the internal UART module within STM32 Microcontrollers.

There are two forms of UART hardware as follows:

- UART – Universal Asynchronous Receiver/Transmitter
- USART – Universal Synchronous/Asynchronous Receiver/Transmitter

The Synchronous type of transmitter generates the data clock and sends it to the receiver which works accordingly in a synchronized manner. On the other hand, the Asynchronous type of transmitter generates the data clock internally. There is no incoming serial clock signal, so to achieve proper communication between the two ends, both of them must be using the same baud rate.

4.4 Basics of UART Communication

Communication plays a significant role in transferring information from one end to another end (source to destination). In this digital landscape where most of the day-to-day tasks are completed through portable devices, communicating the data effectively by utilizing conventional resources is a crucial task. Moreover, with the existence of myriad modes of communication devices and embedded platforms in a single architecture, transferring data without any disturbance or noise in the signal is a time-consuming process. Notably, in a wireless medium such as mobile, telephone, and computers revolving around a microcontroller, enabling security and removing the barrier between transmitter and receiver in terms of latency, granularity, and overhead in real-time is inevitable. To overcome these challenges, numerous researchers have stepped in with a unique data transmission device that empowers users to transfer their data efficiently. In this article, Universal Asynchronous Receiver and transmitter (UART) are discussed along with its features, functionalities, applications, and future scope.

4.4.1 Introduction to UART

The Universal Asynchronous Receiver/Transmitter, acronymed as UART, is an integrated circuit in a computer or a microcontroller used for serial communication. A microcontroller might have one or two peripherals of UART integrated into it. A typical UART module is

operated based on the logic level of the control signal and setting up a similar baud rate on both transmitter and receiver end. Individual data bits are converted in the form of logic high, low, and stop bits to initiate data transmission. The generic features of UART are as follows,

1. Universal Accepted: The speed, data size, and velocity can be configured easily to ascertain the requirements of the clients and follows the same protocol around the world.

2. Short Distance Transmission: UART is frequently used in short-range transmission. In wired communication, the distance can be configured in terms of baud rate.

Baud Rate	Max. Length of Cable (Feet)
19200	50
9600	500
4800	1000
2400	3000

The relationship between the transmission distance and speed in UART is proportional to each other. Shorter distance results in a faster data transfer rate. The transmission distance can vary from a few inches to meters based on desired speed, noise generated due to external source, and quality of the external device.

3. Low-Cost Protocol: The non-requirement of a clock signal and single wire utilization to transmit data keeps the hardware simple, which in turn makes it cost-efficient compared to other data transfer modules.

4.4.2 Basic Block Diagram of UART

The generic block diagram of UART comprises two components namely transmitter and receiver, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure4: UART-communication-interface

In UART, possibilities to exchange data between the transmitter and receiver can be divided into three modes, namely simplex, half-duplex systems, and full-duplex systems. Whether UART functions as a half-duplex or full-duplex system depends on the processor in which it is integrated. Some microcontrollers support half-duplex and some support full-duplex systems. Almost most of the latest microcontrollers support full-duplex systems.

- **Simplex Systems:** In this type of communication, the data bits are transmitted only from a single end (i.e., source device).
- **Half Duplex Systems:** Data transmission can be achieved from either direction, but only one user can transmit data at a time. Since the hardware structure shares the same data bus and control buffer, users are allowed to either receive or transmit data at that particular instant.

- **Full-Duplex Systems:** Data transmission can happen in either direction, both the devices which are communicating through this system can receive and transmit data at the same time and they also have individual data buffers for Tx and Rx.

4.4.3 UART Implementation

The development of a UART module is simple. It requires only two signal pins, namely Transmission (Txd) and Receiver (Rxd). Serial to parallel converter will be placed at the input transmission end and parallel to serial communication at the output to convert signals to the desired voltage level and enhance the speed during low distance transmission. The detailed description of the architecture is explained in the following stages.

Figure5: UART-transmitter-and-receiver-module

As shown in Fig. 5, the transmitter section is further categorized into three stages namely

- Transmitter holding register: This block holds the control of outgoing information and from the UART buffer signal before processing to the next step.
- Transmitter shift register: Once the data is processed from the holding register, this block shifts the data by moving bits from left to right or vice versa until the final bit is transmitted or received. It also converts the input strings from parallel to serial data combinations and transfers the data in the form of bit by bit operation.
- Control Logic: As the name suggests, it controls the data flow between transmitter and receiver, and avoids sending blank/error data during transmission.

Similarly, the receiver block encompasses receive hold register, shift register, and control logic. The functionality is similar to that of the transmitter block, where the collected data is initially processed through a receiver shift register to convert into parallel mode. The receiver holding the converter dispatches the data to the user. Control logic is used to initiate read and write operations.

4.4.4 UART Data Communication Framework

In most communication devices such as computers and microcontrollers, the data transfer is achieved without the requirement of a clock signal to the receiver-leveraging UART

techniques. Before data transmission, both the sender and receiver have to accept the timing parameters by configuring the same baud rate and synchronizing the settings.

Figure 6: UART-data-frame-structure

4.4.5 UART Serial Interface

Two types of signals, namely Txd and Rxd, are used to complete data transmission. Txd signifies the transmission side, which is the output signal from UART. Rxd represents the receiver end and acts as an input signal for UART. The start bit is used to notify the receiver about transferring a bit of data and forcing the receiver clock to synchronize with the transmitter clock frequency. Initially, the transmitter will be at an idle state, driving data lines to logic high. Individual data bits are transferred in a sequence with the least significant bit at the higher order to the most significant bit at a lower order of the data line. The transmission rate should maintain an equal time sequence. When all the data bits are accepted from the receiver end, it evaluates the parity bit and rises the end stop bit. During these processes, the signal can result in framing error if there is no stop bit or variations in the timing sequences. In this condition, irrespective of received bits, UART neglects the start, stop, and parity signal and awaits to receive the new transmitted data bits. Transmission signal enters idle conditions during the absence of input data set.

In UART, the input data packet is considered as a combination of four basic components namely

- Start Bit: High to low-level voltage change represents the start of data transmission
- Input Data: Data stored in the form of bits
- Parity Bit: It is used to evaluate the fault in received data
- Stop Bit: Terminates data transfer

Applications of UART Communication

- Achieving communication amongst distant computers around 900 meters.
- Transferring data through PC serial port.
- Baud rate generation for numerous applications helps to determine the speed of data transmission.
- Microcontroller to implement wireless data communication.
- Bluetooth and GPS modules.

Advantages and Limitations of UART Communication

- Only two communication signals are sufficient to achieve data transmission.
- Non-requirement of clock and timing signals.
- Parity bits to ensure integrated error validation.

Limitations (Disadvantages) of UART Communication

- Limited amount of input data frame.
- Both parties should follow similar data transfer settings.
- The data transfer rate is minimal compared to parallel communication.
- Several masters and slave methodologies are not supported.

4.5 USART in STM32

4.5.1 STM32 USART Highlights

The universal synchronous asynchronous receiver transmitter (USART) offers a flexible means of full-duplex data exchange with external equipment requiring an industry-standard NRZ (Non-Return-To-Zero) asynchronous serial data format. The USART offers a very wide range of baud rates using a fractional baud rate generator. It supports synchronous one-way communication and half-duplex single-wire communication. It also supports the LIN (local interconnection network), Smartcard Protocol and IrDA (infrared data association) SIR ENDEC specifications, and modem operations (CTS/RTS). It allows multiprocessor communication. High-speed data communication is possible by using the DMA for multi-buffer configuration.

4.5.2 STM32 USART Main Features

- Full duplex, asynchronous communications
- Fractional baud rate generator systems – A common programmable transmit and receive baud rates up to 4.5 MBits/s
- Parity control
- Programmable data word length (8 or 9 bits)
- Configurable stop bits – support for 1 or 2 stop bits
- LIN Master Synchronous Break send capability and LIN slave break detection capability
- Transmitter clock output for synchronous transmission
- IrDA SIR Encoder-Decoder – Support for the 3/16-bit duration for normal mode
- Smartcard Emulation Capability
- Single-wire half-duplex communication
- Configurable multi-buffer communication using DMA (direct memory access) – Buffering of received/transmitted bytes in reserved SRAM using centralized DMA
- Separate enable bits for Transmitter and Receiver
- Transfer detection flags: (Receive buffer full – Transmit buffer empty – End of Transmission flags)
- 4 error detection flags: (Overrun error; Noise error; Frame error; Parity error)
- 10 interrupt sources with flags

4.5.3 STM32 USART Hardware Functionalities

In this section, we'll get a deep insight into the STM32 USART module hardware, its block diagram, functionalities, BRG, modes of operations, and data reception/transmission.

Any USART bidirectional communication requires a minimum of two pins: Receive Data In (RX) and Transmit Data Out (TX). Through these pins, serial data is transmitted and received in normal USART

mode. The CK pin is required to interface in synchronous mode. The CTS & RTS pins are required in Hardware flow control mode.

4.5.3.1 USART Block Diagram

As you can easily spot in the digital block diagram for this UART hardware module, there are two separate shift registers and double-buffered in/out data for a full-duplex data transmission and reception operation. Both shift registers which shift in or out the data during reception/transmission are being clocked at the rate of the BRG (baud rate generator) circuitry at the bottom of the diagram.

Figure 7: USART block diagram

There is an address register for multi-processor communication mode. There exist a hardware data flow control unit to support this feature. And also, an IrDA decoder circuitry, and interrupt control unit to generate various interrupt signals on different USART hardware events.

4.5.3.2 USART Data (Character) Packet

Word length may be selected as being either 8 or 9 bits by programming the M bit in the USART_CR1 register. Transmission and reception are driven by a common baud rate generator, the clock for each is generated when the enable bit is set respectively for the transmitter and receiver. The TX pin is in a low state during the start bit. It is in a high state during the stop bit. An Idle character is interpreted as an entire frame of “1” s followed by the start bit of the next frame which contains data (The number of “1” ‘s will include the number of stop bits). A Break character is interpreted as receiving “0” s for a frame period. At the end of the Break frame, the transmitter inserts either 1 or 2 stop bits (logic “1” bit) to acknowledge the start bit.

4.5.3.3 USART Transmitter

The USART transmitter can send data words of either 8 or 9 bits depending on the M bit status. When the transmit enable bit (TE) is set, the data in the transmit shift register is shifted out to the TX pin, and the corresponding clock pulses are output on the CK pin (for synchronous mode).

During a USART transmission, data shifts out the least significant bit first on the TX pin. Every character is preceded by a start bit, which is a logic level low for a one-bit period. The character is terminated by a configurable number of stop bits. The following stop bits are supported by USART: 0.5, 1, 1.5, and 2 stop bits.

5. Conclusion

This report defines what an embedded system is, including in the definition the most complex and recent innovations in the market. It then defined what an embedded systems architecture is in terms of the sum of the various representations (structures) of a system. It also introduced why the architectural approach is used as the approach to introducing embedded concepts in this report, because it presents a clear vision of what the system is, or could be, composed of and how these elements function. In addition, this approach can provide early indicators into what may and may not work in a system, and possibly improve the integrity of a system and lower costs via reusability. The contains the first real-world examples of the report about how industry standards play into an embedded design. Its purpose is to show the importance of knowing and understanding the standards associated with a particular device and leveraging these standards to understand or create an architecture. Furthermore, embedded systems are rapidly becoming a catalyst for change in the computing, data communications, telecommunications, industrial control, and entertainment sectors. Automatic systems in any field will be useful and will save the people and organizations. New innovative applications in these as well as other areas will make embedded systems one of the fastest developing technology of the near future. Thus, the embedded system plays an important role in our day-to-day life.

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